

Grøn Dyst Abstract For Posesystem

Anis Ashfaq, Tobias Pedersen, Troels Kristensen, Vilhelm Pedersen

DTU Diplom, Technical University of Denmark

We want to embed a refund system for plastic bags in Denmark in which consumers can bring the plastic bags sold in supermarkets to a standard-build device inside the supermarkets and receive a refund in the same way they can with regular plastic bottles. Currently there is no proper way to recycle the 450 million plastic bags sold in Denmark each year, which means that many bags are stored away or thrown in the trash. We consider this an unused potential, which could benefit both consumers and the environment - with our concept, plastic bags will be cheaper for the customer and more sustainable for the environment.

First, we want to test our concept in a supermarket to gather data and find out if the concept could become a success. If so, we would expand to supermarkets all over Denmark by cooperating with franchises such as Coop or Dansk Supermarked and/or with Miljøstyrelsen. Our refund machine would be developed by our team specifically for plastic bags and set up in every supermarket alongside the current refund machine. In terms of financing, our initial costs could be covered by sponsoring's from DTU or Grøn Dyst. Otherwise, we would consider cooperating with franchises or providing ourselves.

The concept is developed by four students from DTU in conjunction with a course in green entrepreneurship and our coming company will be called Dansk Plastpose-system.